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Opportunities To Share Ideas & Practice Among Engineering Education Initiatives

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ABSTRACT

Globally there are a significant number of engineering and STEM related initiatives and organisations with each organisation having a particular emphasis, audience or approach regarding development of education in these fields.

All however aim to share ideas and best-practice among engineering educators so improving the overall learning experience of their students. By analysing the nature of the organisations it is hoped synergies can be found to more formally encourage organisations to share ideas while still retaining distinct identities and focuses.

At the SEFI 2016 conference in Tampere the issue of exploring and developing links between SEFI and CDIO (Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate) was raised.

This paper will share work being done towards a SEFI (European Engineering Education Society) position paper to improve the links between it and the CDIO initiative.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Engineering Education Research, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: SEFI, CDIO, Collaboration

INTRODUCTION

Around the globe there are a number of organisations and initiatives focussed around supporting and developing engineering education at which recognise the distinct demands, expectations and goals of the discipline.

Each organisation will have its own particular remit which may be focussed around specific branches of engineering, may be geographically focussed or may have

particular emphasis such as engineering education research, practical implementation or focus on aspects such as technology to support education.

With pressures on academic staff to often focus their personal development around scientific and technical research, Engineering Education innovation is often characterised by small numbers of individuals working in the field in their own institution. The involvement of particular universities in these organisations is often dependent on key individual academic's personal contacts, capacity and aspirations.

While this is understandable, there could therefore be a tendency for parallel communities to develop which miss some potential synergies to support their members.

At the 2016 SEFI conference in Tampere there were a number of discussions regarding opportunities for closer collaboration between the European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) and Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate (CDIO) with a view to developing a corresponding SEFI position paper.

This paper looks at these two organisations and draws together some thoughts on opportunities for collaboration.

1 ENGINEERING EDUCATION ORGANISATIONS

1.1 The global landscape

Globally there are a number of engineering education initiatives including the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE), European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), International Society for Engineering Pedagogy (IGIP) and Conceive, Design, Implement & Operate (CDIO).

For the purposes of this paper, the focus will be on the relationship and synergies between SEFI and CDIO.

The reason for focussing on these initiatives relates to overlapping but distinct educational and geographical focuses which offer potential synergies while still acknowledging the different strengths and objectives of each initiative.

2 SEFI AND CDIO

2.1 SEFI

SEFI (Société Européenne pour la Formation des Ingénieurs / European Society for Engineering Education) was established in 1973 in Belgium by a consortium of 21 European Universities from 6 countries with a mission *“To contribute to the development and improvement of engineering education in Europe and to the enhancement of the image of both engineering education and engineering professionals in Society”*. [1]

It lists a number of objectives including acting as a networking organisation among academics, industry and international bodies, serving as a forum to develop and influence policies related to engineering education and to contribute to the development and the improvement of higher engineering education.

SEFI offers membership as an individual, an institution, on a corporate basis or an associate basis – typically professional bodies, non-European organisations, student

groups etc. At present SEFI has around 130 institutional members who pay an annual subscription to support the upkeep of the organisation.

SEFI runs an annual conference and is also responsible for the European Journal of Engineering Education. Organisationally SEFI is run by a council with responsibility for specific themes devolved to 11 working groups. These thematic groups have a range of responsibilities such as subject area (Mathematics, Physics, Sustainability, Ethics), operational aspects (Curriculum development, Quality, Online education) together with a range of other areas (Gender & Diversity, Education Research, Lifelong Learning).

These groups are then charged with developing their respective fields through projects, position papers and through the support and review of papers to the annual conference. Recent position papers emerging from SEFI include those on skills (2015/16) and those on the accreditation of engineering education (2012).

2.2 CDIO

CDIO emerged toward the end of the 1990s following thinking at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's (MIT's) aerospace group which showed concerns among engineering employers that graduates emerging from Universities were often strong in engineering science but tended to lack many of the practical and personal qualities required by industry. While voiced at MIT, this was quickly seen as a global issue and a reflection of the culture of Universities moving toward a research driven agenda which in turn informed staff appointment and other strategic decisions.

By the turn of millennia a consortium involving MIT and a number of Scandinavian Universities began to develop the CDIO approach centred initially around a syllabus focussing on "what to teach" based on consultation with stakeholders. Later 12 standards were created which tended to focus on "how to teach" with the focus being on active and project based approaches and continuous improvement of provision in an effort to draw out many of the perceived deficiencies in conventional graduates. The Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate (CDIO) was coined to reflect the sort of stages a student or graduate engineer might go through in the holistic solving of a typical engineering problem. [2]

At the time of writing, the initiative has grown to around 130 institutions globally, organised into 7 geographical regions. The initiative annually organises a main summer conference, a Fall (Autumn) meeting together with at least one meeting held by each region per annum.

Membership is at institutional level and carries no subscription cost. Potential new members are expected to benchmark themselves using a 0-5 rubric on each of the CDIO standards and present their plans at a regional or international meeting. There is no requirement to score any particular number of points against the standards however the CDIO organising council expect to see commitment to the CDIO approach, senior management support from their institution and a clear indication of how they would hope to participate in CDIO activities going forward.

For a typical CDIO member, initial involvement may often be triggered by a desire for their institution to make a step-change away from relatively traditional programmes to ones with a more holistic, active and project based approach. The CDIO standards

and networks can then be used to help manage, measure and inform this change process.

For more established members, CDIO perhaps takes on a more conventional form, acting as a network for sharing best practice and innovation. In recent years a stronger focus has been made in regard to developing stronger engineering education research rigour and methodologies with the aim to provide continuing benefits to more long standing members.

Table 1 : A comparison between SEFI and CDIO

	CDIO	SEFI
Established	2001	1973
Institutional Members (Global/Europe)	~130/~75	~133/~133
Membership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional only (No fee, elected following successful presentation showing commitment to CDIO principles) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional Individual Industrial Associate (eg. Professional Body, Industrial Organisation) All by subscription
Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CDIO Council 2 Co-chairs 6 Members at Large 7 Regional leadership teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SEFI Board of Directors 21 members plus President & 2 Vice-Presidents
Devolved Responsibility	7 Regions	11 Working Groups
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main Summer Conference (June) Fall Meeting (November) 1-2 Regional Meetings per region / per year Regular TELECONS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main Summer Conference (September) Working group events Board meetings
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CDIO Conference Proceedings Fall and Regional Meeting Documentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SEFI Conference Proceedings Annual Report EJEE (6 issues pa)

3 MEMBERSHIP AND FOCUS

3.1 Membership

SEFI has around 130 institutional members in Europe, while CDIO has around 80 members within its European and UK & Ireland regions, with a further 50 or so institutional members around the globe. The memberships of both of these organisations has grown organically over the years since their respective launches.

More detailed analysis of the breakdown of the memberships shows some interesting patterns and opportunities. [3], [4]

Fig. 1 shows the membership breakdown for some of the most heavily involved nations. It can be seen that there are a number of observations which can be made.

- Institutions typically belong to one or other but not necessarily both despite the possible overlapping and complementary opportunities afforded by this.
- There can be an apparent geographical bias toward SEFI (eg. France), or CDIO (Russia) which is likely due to history or local influences in each case.
- The membership levels of both institutions do not necessarily correlate to the number of engineering education providers in each country. Thus Finland and Sweden have a similar number of members of SEFI and/or CDIO as much larger countries such as France, Germany and the UK.

Number of institutional members of SEFI and CDIO by country

Fig. 1 . Number of institutional members of SEFI and CDIO by country

To reinforce the independence of the two organisations, *Fig. 2* shows the degree of overlap between the two organisations within Europe. It is notable that only around 10% of institutions holding membership of either organisation formally participate in both.

European institutional membership of SEFI & CDIO - Overlap and independence

Fig. 2. European institutional membership of SEFI & CDIO - Overlap and independence.

It is also observable that both organisations have scope for growth in some of the larger markets should they choose to. As an example Fig 3. shows the extent of CDIO and SEFI membership within the UK market showing only around 10% of institutions awarding engineering degrees are members of either organisation. In the UK market, there may be particular appetite for growth with the introduction of the “Teaching Excellence Framework” (TEF) which has put some pressure on Higher Education providers to develop their approaches to learning and teaching. [5],[6]

United Kingdom engineering degree awarding institutions membership of SEFI & CDIO

Fig. 3 . United Kingdom engineering degree awarding institutions by membership of SEFI & CDIO

3.2 Focus

Both SEFI and CDIO have annual conferences where they invite members and any other interested partners to share their latest ideas, findings and research. In 2016 both conferences were held in Finland. In June the CDIO conference was held at Turku University of Applied Science where just under 100 papers were presented,

- That by sharing engineering education research proposals across the joint SEFI and CDIO networks, there is a much greater chance of finding like-minded partners, giving stronger overall partnerships, greater likelihood of securing funding and better overall project outcomes.
- That all engineering education specialists face a range of common practical pressures related to demands on staff time, expectations and budgetary and resource concerns. By working together SEFI and CDIO have greater critical mass to help influence the decision makers at institutional and governmental level to recognise the value and importance of engineering education.
- That both organisations have their own distinctive profiles and objectives and while sharing many core values, each offers the practising academic, support and tools to help them achieve their personal and institutional objectives.
- That, as exemplified by the 20 or so institutions holding memberships in both SEFI and CDIO, involvement in both institutions is a positive experience.
- That to make such interactions possible both CDIO and SEFI should be open to joint initiatives and offer platforms to raise awareness of each others activities both among existing members but also to the sizable engineering education

REFERENCES

- [1] SEFI Mission / Objectives / Values, http://www.sefi.be/?page_id=6811 [Accessed: 25 April 2017]
- [2] Crawley E.F., Malmqvist J., Östlund, S., (2014) Rethinking Engineering Education: The CDIO Approach, Springer
- [3] SEFI Institutional Members, http://www.sefi.be/?page_id=44 [Accessed: 25 April 2017]
- [4] CDIO Member Schools, <http://www.cdio.org/cdio-collaborators/school-profiles> [Accessed: 25 April 2017]
- [5] Robinson, W, Hilli. A (2016), «Teaching Excellence Framework» and Professionalising Teaching and Learning in Research-Intensive Universities: An Exploration of Opportunities, Challenges, Rewards and Values from a Recent Empirical Study, *Foro de Educación*, Vol 14, Iss 21, Pp 151-165
- [6] Wood, M, Su, F (2017) What makes an excellent lecturer? Academics' perspectives on the discourse of 'teaching excellence' in higher education, *Teaching in Higher Education*, Vol 22, Issue 4, pp. 451-466
- [7] Proceedings 44th SEFI Conference, 12-15 September 2016, Tampere, Finland
- [8] Proceedings 12th International CDIO Conference, 12-16 June 2016, Turku, Finland